

1 **Myogenic factors that support rejuvenation and sustain youth in humans.**

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7 We studied total gene expression in muscle derived stem cells and in iPS stem cell derived mesodermal
8 progenitors for discovery of novel, myogenic-type factors associated with rejuvenation in humans. We
9 report here discovery of myogenic factor 5, encoded by *Myf5* in the muscle stem cell in humans.

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11 Citations

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